

TRB Proteins in Moss Reveal Evolutionarily Conserved Roles in Plant Development and Telomere Maintenance

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Supplementary Figures

(a)

PpTRB1

(b)

PpTRB2

(c)

PpTRB3

Supplementary Figure 1. Schematic representation of mutant lines. (a) Diagram of *PpTRB1* locus indicating the site of incorporated mutations. Nucleotide positions are given relative to the ATG codon, with adenine designated as position +1. Diagrams of *PpTRB2* (b) and *PpTRB3* (c) loci showing the locations of knockout cassettes containing homologous arms flanking the selectable marker gene, along with positions of genotyping primers. Notably, non-specific transcriptional upregulation downstream of the 35S-HygR-NosT selection cassette — used for homologous recombination-based mutagenesis — was observed in *pptrb2* and *pptrb3* lines.

Supplementary Figure 2. Representative images of all verified mutant lines, prepared as described in the Methods section. For the mutant analysis, multiple lines were generated for each representative mutant (single and double). Single representative line was selected for further investigation and is also depicted in Figure 1: *pptrb1 #5*, *pptrb2 #11*, *pptrb3 #2*, *pptrb1 pptrb2 #3*, *pptrb1 pptrb3 #6* and *pptrb2 pptrb3 #16*.

Supplementary Figure 3. Validation of disrupted gene transcription in *pptrb* lines using QuantSeq. RNA-Seq QuantSeq, which selectively captures the 3' ends of polyadenylated transcripts, was employed to assess transcript abundance in *PpTRB1*, *PpTRB2*, and *PpTRB3* loci. Sequencing reads were aligned to the corresponding genomic regions, and the results were visualized using the Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV) with both v3.3 and v6.1 genome annotations. Schematic diagrams of the mutations and deletions characterizing each *pptrb* mutant line are presented alongside the mapped read profiles. IGV peak patterns revealed a clear knock-down of *PpTRB1* expression in *pptrb1* mutants and complete knock-out of *PpTRB2* and *PpTRB3* expression in *pptrb2* and *pptrb3* mutant lines, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 4. The transition of chloronema to caulonema in the dark. Mosses grown under light conditions for one week were transferred to darkness for three weeks. Under these conditions, WT plants developed long, negatively gravitropic caulonemata, while *pptrb2*, *pptrb3*, and all double mutants exhibited a significant reduction in caulonemal growth. **(a)** A 50 μ l aliquot of the homogenized protonema, collected during the mosses' passaging, was spotted onto the plate. **(b)** A small piece (approximately 1 mm²) from a one-week-old colony was transferred onto the plate.

Supplementary Figure 5. Differential gene expression in *pptrb* mutants. Venn diagram illustrating the overlap of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) among *pptrb* single and double mutants using the reference genome v6.1. The total number of DEGs, as well as the subsets of up-regulated and down-regulated genes, are indicated.

Volcanoplots for top 20 genes

Significance: ● not significant ● padj<0.05

Supplementary Figure 6. Volcano plots of differentially expressed genes between WT and *pptrb* single and double mutant lines. Volcano plots illustrate the differential gene expression profiles between wild-type (WT) and *pptrb* mutant lines using the reference genome v3.3. The top 20 differentially expressed genes are labeled with their corresponding *Pp* gene identifiers. Genes were considered significantly differentially expressed if they met the thresholds of $p < 0.05$ and absolute fold change > 1 . Red dots represent significantly altered genes, while black dots denote genes that do not meet the significance criteria.

Supplementary Figure 9. Analysis of RNAseq data from single and double *pptrb* mutant lines in GOLEM web-tool for the presence of *cis*-regulatory motifs. The GOLEM tool (Nevosád *et al.*, 2025) was used to analyze RNA-Seq data from wild-type (WT) and *pptrb* mutant plants for the presence and positional distribution of *cis*-regulatory motifs relative to the transcription start site (TSS). The analysis revealed several regulatory motifs in the promoter regions of genes with the highest expression levels in *pptrb* mutants. Notably, the *telo*-box motif was more frequently observed in promoters of highly expressed genes in *pptrb1*, *pptrb3*, *pptrb1 pptrb3* and *pptrb2 pptrb3* mutants compared to WT (GLMM, negative binomial distribution, emmeans post-hoc, Benjamini Hochberg correction). In contrast, the JM14 and Site II motifs—previously linked to TRB protein function—did not show such difference in *pptrb* mutants when compared to WT. Analyses were performed using the *P. patens* reference genome v3.3. The detailed procedure for statistical analysis can be found in the main text.

Supplementary Figure 10. Telomere length analysis by TRF assay in single and double *pptrb* mutant lines across various mutant lines. DNA was extracted at different passage and subjected to terminal restriction fragment (TRF) analysis. DNA molecular weight markers (kb) are shown.

Supplementary Figure 11. PpTRB proteins localize to the nucleus and nucleolus. PpTRB proteins were fused with GFP and transfected into *P. patens* protoplasts together with mRFP-Fibrillarin, which labels the nucleolus. PpTRB1 and PpTRB2 proteins localize to the nucleus, while PpTRB3 localizes only to the nucleolus. Individual channels representing Bright Field (BF), RFP, GFP and chloroplast autofluorescence are shown. *Merge I* displays the merged channels of RFP, YFP, and chloroplast autofluorescence. *Merge II* displays the merged channels of BF, RFP, YFP, and chloroplast autofluorescence. Scale bars = 5 μ m.

Supplementary Figure 12. PpTRBs mutually interact in the nucleus. Protein–protein interactions among *PpTRB* proteins were analysed using a Bimolecular Fluorescence Complementation (BiFC) assay. *PpTRB* constructs fused to either the N-terminal (nYFP) or C-terminal (cYFP) fragments of YFP were co-expressed in protoplasts derived from 7-day-old *P. patens* protonema. Fluorescence signals were visualized in individual channels. YFP channel images reveal distinct fluorescent foci localized within the nucleus, indicating physical interactions between *PpTRB* proteins. *Merge I* displays a merged channels of RFP, YFP, and chloroplast autofluorescence. *Merge II* includes bright-field (BF) in addition to RFP, YFP, and chloroplast autofluorescence channels. Scale bars = 5 μm .

Supplementary Figure 13. PpTRBs mutually interact in the cytoplasm. Protein–protein interactions among *PpTRB* proteins were investigated using a Bimolecular Fluorescence Complementation (BiFC) assay. Constructs encoding *PpTRBs* fused to either the N-terminal (nYFP) or C-terminal (cYFP) fragments of YFP were co-expressed in protoplasts isolated from 7-day-old *P. patens* protonema. Fluorescence signals are shown as individual channels. In the YFP channel, fluorescent foci are observed in the cytoplasm, indicating interactions occurring outside the nucleus. *Merge I* shows the overlay of RFP, YFP, and chloroplast autofluorescence signals. *Merge II* includes bright-field (BF) along with RFP, YFP, and chloroplast autofluorescence. Scale bars = 5 μm .

Supplementary Figure 14. Maximum intensity projections and z-stacks of PpTRB protein interactions in the cytoplasm. Protein–protein interactions among PpTRB proteins were examined using BiFC in *P. patens* protoplasts derived from 7-day-old protonema cells and visualized by confocal microscopy. Panels show (I) maximum intensity projections of complete z-stacks and (II) representative single-plane sections of protoplasts (PpTRB1 with PpTRB1 – 0.52 μm each z-step size; PpTRB1 with PpTRB2 – 0.47 μm each z-step size; PpTRB1 with PpTRB3 0.47 μm each z-step size), scale bars = 5 μm .

Supplementary Figure 15. PpTRBs nuclear speckles locate at same spots in nucleoplasm. Representative confocal microscopy images show the subnuclear localization of *PpTRB* proteins fused to GFP or RFP. Merged images reveal co-localization of *PpTRBs* at discrete nuclear foci. Scale bars = 5 μm . Intensity profiles corresponding to regions of interest (indicated by red arrows) confirm overlapping fluorescence signals, indicating co-localization of *PpTRBs* in nuclear speckles.

Supplementary Figure 16. Calculated FRET efficiency from speckles and nucleoplasm for PpTRB interactions. FRET efficiency E (%) was calculated as $E = (1 - \tau_{DA} / \tau_D) \times 100\%$, where τ_{DA} is the donor fluorescence lifetime in the presence of the acceptor, and τ_D is the donor lifetime in the absence of the acceptor. Statistical differences were determined by two-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparison test ($P < 0.05$).

Tree scale: 1

Supplementary Figure 17. Phylogenetic analysis of TRB proteins across streptophyte taxa. Maximum likelihood (ML) phylogenetic trees were constructed to examine the evolutionary relationships of TRB proteins from various species, with accession numbers indicated for each sequence. Branch support was evaluated using ultrafast bootstrap approximation with 10,000 replicates; bootstrap values are shown below the branches. The trees were visualized using iTOL v6 (Letunic and Bork, 2024). Within Spermatophyta, TRB proteins segregate into two distinct clades, represented by light and dark green branches, highlighting their divergence in seed plants.

References

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